

Design simulation and analysis of an MPPT technique using ANN integral backstepping and SMC for PV systems

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ABSTRACT

This paper introduces the design of an innovative hybrid MPPT method called artificial neural networks-integral backstepping sliding mode control (ANN-IBSMC). This approach combines artificial neural networks (ANNs), which output the maximum power point voltage using inputs such as irradiance and temperature, with a robust control strategy. The designed controller aims to track the reference voltage with high accuracy and responsiveness by modifying the pulse width modulation of the DC-DC converter in the photovoltaic system. The IBSMC integrates the advantages of two control methods: the stability and accuracy of integral backstepping, and the robustness and fast response of sliding mode control (SMC). This combination enables improved precision, high convergence speed, enhanced robustness, and strong stability, the latter being ensured by the Lyapunov function. To evaluate the performance of the proposed controller, a comparative study is performed against other hybrid control techniques, such as the ANN-backstepping controller, the ANN-integral sliding mode controller, and the ANN-backstepping sliding mode controller, using MATLAB/Simulink. A sensitivity and robustness analysis was carried out.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The worldwide demand for energy continues its rapid growth, driven by the expansion in large-scale industrial production. However, the use of fossil fuels poses a major threat to humanity and the ecosystems of our planet. Addressing this challenge necessitates replacing these polluting energy sources with renewable energies to combat global warming. Against this backdrop, optimizing energy production from renewable energy sources has become a primary objective for researchers specializing in control systems and energy efficiency. The maximum utilization of solar energy through photovoltaic (PV) panels has seen significant advancements. However, electrical generation based on solar input depends heavily on variations in irradiance and temperature, making energy yield optimization a complex task. To maximize electrical output, the system's operating point must remain at the maximum power point (MPP). This requires regulating the converter so that the PV module's voltage consistently matches the MPP voltage, regardless of meteorological variations.

Numerous researchers have developed and studied various control techniques to track and maintain the MPP under changing weather conditions. Key performance criteria include convergence speed, accuracy, stability, and robustness, all of which are crucial for optimal utilization of this inexhaustible energy source. Several studies [1], [2] have proposed early maximum power point tracking (MPPT) techniques based on conventional approaches such as perturb & observe (P&O) and hill-climbing. Other studies [3], [4] have focused on the incremental conductance method, while additional strategies relying on open-circuit voltage and

fractional short-circuit current have also been investigated. However, these conventional methods exhibit significant limitations, leading to an inherent trade-off between tracking speed, accuracy, and system stability.

To overcome these limitations, several studies [5], [6] have developed controllers based on advanced approaches, such as sliding mode control (SMC) and backstepping, to enhance the operational performance of PV systems. Sliding mode control is characterized by high robustness and fast convergence under varying climatic conditions but suffers from the chattering phenomenon, which may degrade system stability. In contrast, the backstepping control ensures high stability and tracking precision based on Lyapunov theory, at the cost of increased design complexity and sensitivity to parameter uncertainties. Additionally, intelligent MPPT techniques, such as those based on fuzzy logic [7], particle swarm optimization (PSO), or artificial neural networks (ANN) [8], have emerged. Several studies [9], [10] have shown that fuzzy logic exhibits good adaptive stability, although it offers limited precision strongly dependent on predefined rules. Other works [11], [12] have demonstrated that the PSO algorithm ensures fast and stable convergence toward the global maximum power point but may produce slight residual oscillations if parameters are not properly tuned. Other studies based on ANN methods [13], [14] have highlighted their high accuracy and rapid response due to learning capabilities, although robustness may decrease outside the trained operating domain. Recently, hybrid controllers combining conventional, intelligent, and advanced approaches have been proposed, including backstepping–P&O, ANN–backstepping, and ANN–sliding mode controllers. These hybrid techniques aim to simultaneously enhance stability, robustness, and tracking speed of the MPP. For instance, the backstepping–P&O controller provides a good compromise between speed and stability, though it remains less accurate under rapid irradiance variations. Previous studies [15], [16] have shown that ANN–backstepping offers high precision and stability but with a slightly slower convergence time. Similarly, other works [17], [18] have demonstrated that ANN–SMC combines the robustness of SMC with the predictive capability of ANN, while still presenting residual chattering issues. Each technique presents its own advantages and limitations, imposing an inevitable trade-off between speed, precision, robustness, and stability. Consequently, current research trends focus on the development of advanced control strategies capable of reducing, or even eliminating, this trade-off inherent to the performance of photovoltaic systems.

This study proposes a new integrated control strategy, referred to as the artificial neural networks–integral backstepping sliding mode controller (ANN–IBSMC). This hybrid approach coherently combines artificial intelligence with advanced nonlinear control by leveraging the predictive capability of the artificial neural network, the stability and accuracy provided by the integral backstepping method [19], [20], and the robustness and fast response of SMC [21], [22]. The overall stability of the system is ensured by the Lyapunov function, making this synergy an effective way to unify the strengths of each control method. The ANN generates a reference voltage V_{REF} corresponding to the maximum available power for each meteorological variation. The main novel contribution of this method lies in its ability to simultaneously reduce the trade-off between speed, accuracy, robustness, and stability, thereby outperforming previously reported hybrid techniques such as ANN–backstepping [23]–[25], ANN–ISMC [26], [27], and ANN–BSMC [28]. The performance of the ANN–IBSMC controller has been evaluated and compared under various weather conditions using MATLAB/Simulink, demonstrating rapid convergence, high accuracy, and enhanced robustness. A sensitivity and robustness study of this controller has been carried out.

2. MODELLING OF THE PHOTOVOLTAIC SYSTEM

The photovoltaic system consists of a solar panel and a DC-DC boost converter, with a load connected at the output, as shown in Figure 1. In the proposed controller, the artificial neural network generates the system's reference voltage in real time according to the irradiance and temperature experienced by the photovoltaic panel. The integral backstepping sliding mode control (IBSMC) then applies the control law to the MOSFET to track this reference voltage and ensure efficient power transfer to the load.

2.1. Modelling of PV module

The primary element in a solar module is the solar cell. Figure 2 shows the equivalent electrical schematic for the solar cell. Where I_{ph} is the photocurrent, I_{out} the output current, and I_{sat} the saturation current. V_{out} denotes the output voltage, with R_s and R_{sh} representing series and shunt resistances. Constants like Boltzmann's constant k , the ideality factor a , temperature T , and electron charge q are also involved. Temperature effects are accounted for using K_i , dT , and K_v . Solar irradiance is represented by G and its nominal value G_n , while I_{cc} and V_{oc} stand for short-circuit current and open-circuit voltage, respectively.

$$I_{out} = I_{ph} - I_{sat} \left(e^{\frac{q(V_{out} + (I_{out} * R_s))}{a * k * T}} - 1 \right) - \frac{V_{out} + I_{out} * R_s}{R_{sh}} \quad (1)$$

With:

$$I_{ph} = (I_{cc} + K_i * dT) * \frac{G}{G_n} \tag{2}$$

$$I_{sat} = \frac{I_{cc} + K_i * dT}{e^{\frac{q * (V_{oc} + (K_v * dT))}{a * k * T}} - 1} \tag{3}$$

The photovoltaic module used in the simulation has a maximum power (Pmax) of 240 W, achieved at a voltage of 30.05 V (Vmp) and a current of 7.99 A (Imp). Its open-circuit voltage (Voc) is 37.58 V, while the short-circuit current (Isc) reaches 8.49 A. The temperature coefficient of the short-circuit current (Ki) is 0.15 mA/°C. The module consists of 60 cells (Ns).

Figure 3 illustrates the power-voltage characteristics of the photovoltaic module for different irradiances (1 kW/m², 0.7 kW/m², and 0.5 kW/m² at a temperature of 25 °C) and different temperatures (25 °C, 30 °C, and 50 °C at an irradiances of 1 kW/m²), with the maximum power point varying according to these meteorological conditions. Therefore, for each variation in these two inputs, a specific voltage will correspond to the maximum power point. For optimal and efficient conversion, the system's operating point must be set at the maximum power point for each variation in meteorological conditions.

Figure 1. System PV

Figure 2. Electrical representation of a PV solar cell

Figure 3. Power-voltage characteristic: (a) under varying irradiance levels and (b) at various temperatures

2.2. Modeling of DC-DC converter boost converter

The DC-DC converter alters the amplitude of the input voltage, either decreasing or increasing it, or performing both actions based on the system's output requirements, as described in [29], [30]. The study

focuses on the boost converter, as shown in Figure 4, which increases the PV voltage to a value three times higher at the output, typically around 100 V, depending on the weather conditions. This amplitude change is achieved by varying the converter's duty cycle through the applied control technique.

By applying Kirchhoff's voltage laws during the boost DC-DC converter's on and off intervals of the MOSFET transistor, we obtain (4).

$$\begin{cases} \dot{V}_{PV} = \frac{1}{C_{PV}} I_{PV} - \frac{1}{C_{PV}} I_L \\ \dot{I}_L = \frac{1}{L} V_{PV} - \frac{1}{L} (1 - U) V_{OUT} \\ \dot{V}_{OUT} = \frac{1}{C_{OUT}} (1 - U) I_L - \frac{1}{C_{OUT}} I_{OUT} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

The voltage across the photovoltaic module is represented by V_{PV} , the voltage at the converter's output by V_{OUT} , the current generated by the PV module, denoted I_{PV} , output current by I_{OUT} , and the current flowing through the inductor by I_L . The MOSFET's duty cycle is represented by U , and the output capacitor, input capacitor, and inductance are represented by C_{OUT} , C_{PV} and L , respectively.

Figure 4. Electrical diagram of the boost converter

3. CONTROL OF THE SYSTEM

The proposed approach is based on the combination of the ANN and the IBSMC for controlling the photovoltaic system. The ANN, with its predictive and adaptive capabilities, can provide real-time estimates of the system's uncertainties and nonlinearities. The IBSMC controller is designed to use these estimates to achieve precise tracking of the reference voltage while maintaining robustness and fast response against disturbances and meteorological variations. This synergy will combine the strengths of each technique, leveraging the adaptability and predictive capability of the ANN together with the precision and robustness of the IBSMC, providing a promising framework for effective and stable control.

3.1. Artificial neural networks

Previous studies [31], [32] have described that an ANN, inspired by the functioning of biological neurons, links inputs to outputs through mathematical equations. The efficiency of the network mainly depends on the quality of the database, the number of hidden layers, and the adopted learning algorithm. In this work, the training process was carried out using 80 input cases, with irradiance ranging from 100 to 1000 W/m² and temperature varying between 5 °C and 60 °C. The ANN generates a reference voltage V_{REF} corresponding to the maximum power point voltage V_{MPP} . The designed architecture consists of an input layer (irradiance, temperature), one hidden layer with 50 neurons, and an output layer that presents the desired voltage. The Bayesian regularization algorithm was adopted to ensure good generalization, even with noisy inputs.

Figure 5 illustrates the training performance of the artificial neural network. The training error decreases rapidly during the first iterations and stabilizes after approximately 100 epochs. The best performance is achieved at epoch 810, with a mean squared error of 7.02×10^{-6} . The relatively small gap between the training and testing curves indicates that the model does not suffer from overfitting and retains strong generalization ability. These results confirm the stability and reliability of the ANN training process, ensuring accurate estimation of the nonlinear parameters of the photovoltaic system over a wide range of operating conditions. The minimal deviation observed confirms the strong generalization capability of the network on unseen data. Figure 6 shows the correlation between the ANN-predicted outputs and the target

values. The three plots correspond respectively to the training, testing, and overall datasets. In all cases, the correlation coefficient R reaches 1, indicating a very strong agreement between predicted and actual targets. This high accuracy demonstrates that the ANN effectively learned the nonlinear relationship between the photovoltaic system input parameters and the maximum power point.

Figure 5. Performances of the ANN

Figure 6. Performances and regression of ANN

3.2. Artificial neural networks-integral backstepping sliding mode control

The ANN-IBSMC is a hybrid MPPT approach that combines the artificial neural network with a control structure consisting of backstepping with its integral action, and SMC. The overall system stability ensured by the Lyapunov function, whose derivative remains strictly negative, thereby guaranteeing error convergence and stability against external disturbances and parametric uncertainties. The modeling of this technique is presented as (5).

$$\begin{cases} \dot{V}_{PV} = \frac{1}{C_{PV}} I_{PV} - \frac{1}{C_{PV}} I_L \\ \dot{I}_L = \frac{1}{L} V_{PV} - \frac{1}{L} (1 - U) V_{OUT} \end{cases} \tag{5}$$

The voltage tracking error between V_{PV} and V_{REF} is defined by (6).

$$\epsilon_1 = V_{PV} - V_{REF} \tag{6}$$

The derivative with regard to the time of ε_1 is given by (7).

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_1 = \dot{V}_{PV} - \dot{V}_{REF} = \frac{1}{C_{PV}} I_{PV} - \frac{1}{C_{PV}} I_L - \dot{V}_{REF} \quad (7)$$

The integral action error added to the control law as (8).

$$e_1 = \varepsilon_1 + \zeta \quad (8)$$

With the integral function is defined by (9).

$$\zeta = K \int (V_{PV} - V_{REF}) \quad (9)$$

The first Lyapunov candidate function as (10).

$$V_1 = \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon_1^2 + \frac{1}{2} K \zeta^2 \quad (10)$$

The derivative of (10) is (11).

$$\dot{V}_1 = \varepsilon_1 \dot{\varepsilon}_1 + K \zeta \dot{\zeta} = \varepsilon_1 \left(\frac{1}{C_{PV}} I_{PV} - \frac{1}{C_{PV}} I_L - \dot{V}_{REF} + K \zeta \right) \quad (11)$$

In the case that \dot{V}_1 is negative with $K_1 > 0$, we have (12).

$$\frac{1}{C_{PV}} I_{PV} - \frac{1}{C_{PV}} I_L - \dot{V}_{REF} + K \zeta = -K_1 \varepsilon_1 \quad (12)$$

Based on (12), the reference inductor current controller can be derived as (13) ($\alpha_1 = I_{L.ref}$).

$$\frac{1}{C_{PV}} I_{PV} - \frac{1}{C_{PV}} \alpha_1 - \dot{V}_{REF} + K \zeta = -K_1 \varepsilon_1 \quad (13)$$

$$\alpha_1 = C_{PV} (K_1 \varepsilon_1 - \dot{V}_{REF} + K \zeta) + I_{PV} \quad (14)$$

The derivative of (14) is (15).

$$\dot{\alpha}_1 = C_{PV} (K_1 \dot{\varepsilon}_1 - \dot{V}_{REF} + K \dot{\zeta}) + \dot{I}_{PV} \quad (15)$$

Step 2: In this step, the controller output from the first step α_1 is selected as the control variable. A second error signal is then defined.

$$\varepsilon_2 = I_L - \alpha_1 \quad (16)$$

The (11) and (12) become respectively (17) and (18).

$$\dot{V}_1 = \varepsilon_1 \left(\frac{1}{C_{PV}} I_{PV} - \frac{1}{C_{PV}} (\varepsilon_2 + \alpha_1) - \dot{V}_{REF} + K \zeta \right) \quad (17)$$

$$\frac{1}{C_{PV}} I_{PV} - \frac{1}{C_{PV}} (\varepsilon_2 + \alpha_1) - \dot{V}_{REF} + K \zeta = -K_1 \varepsilon_1 - \frac{\varepsilon_2}{C_{PV}} \quad (18)$$

The sliding surface is given by $s = \varepsilon_2$ the derivative of (16) is (19).

$$\dot{s} = \dot{\varepsilon}_2 = \dot{I}_L - \dot{\alpha}_1 = \frac{1}{L} V_{PV} - \frac{1}{L} (1 - U) V_{OUT} - (C_{PV} (K_1 \dot{\varepsilon}_1 - \dot{V}_{REF} + K \dot{\zeta}) + \dot{I}_{PV}) \quad (19)$$

To guarantee the convergence of the two errors, the second Lyapunov function is selected as (20).

$$V_2 = V_1 + \frac{1}{2} s^2 \quad (20)$$

The derivative of (20) is (21).

$$\dot{V}_2 = \dot{V}_1 + s\dot{s} = -K_1\varepsilon_1^2 + s\left(-\frac{\varepsilon_1}{C_{PV}} + \dot{s}\right) \quad (21)$$

Selecting the exponential reaching law expressed as (22).

$$-\frac{\varepsilon_1}{C_{PV}} + \dot{s} = -C_3(C_1s + C_2\text{Sign}(s)) \quad (22)$$

Replacing \dot{s} in (22) with its expression from (19), we obtain (23).

$$\begin{aligned} &-\frac{\varepsilon_1}{C_{PV}} + \frac{1}{L}V_{PV} - \frac{1}{L}(1-U)V_{OUT} - (C_{PV}(K_1(-K_1\varepsilon_1 - \frac{s}{C_{PV}}) - \dot{V}_{REF} + K\varepsilon_1) + \dot{I}_{PV}) \\ &= -C_3(C_1s + C_2\text{Sign}(s)) \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

The expression for the control input determined as (24).

$$U_{IBSMC} = 1 + \frac{L}{V_{OUT}}\left(C_3(C_1s + C_2\text{Sign}(s)) + C_{PV}\left(K\varepsilon_1 - \dot{V}_{REF} + K_1\left(-\frac{s}{C_{PV}} - K_1\varepsilon_1\right)\right) + \dot{I}_{PV} + \frac{\varepsilon_1}{C_{PV}} - \frac{V_{PV}}{L}\right) \quad (24)$$

Replacing (21) with its expression from (22), we obtain (25).

$$\dot{V}_2 = -K_1\varepsilon_1^2 - C_3s(C_1s + C_2\text{Sign}(s)) < 0 \quad (25)$$

With C_1 , C_2 and C_3 should be positive. This ensures the asymptotic convergence of ε_1 and ε_2 to zero, which in turn guarantees the convergence of V_{PV} toward V_{REF} .

To evaluate the performance of the proposed controller, a comparative study is conducted with other hybrid control approaches. Three main combinations are considered, ANN–backstepping as in (26), proposed in [23]–[25], which combines the adaptive capabilities of the ANN with the stability of classical backstepping; ANN–ISMC (28) proposed in [26], [27], which integrates the ANN with the robustness of integral SMC; and finally, ANN–BSMC (30) proposed in [28], which combines both the stability of backstepping and the robustness of SMC with the ANN. This comparison illustrates how the combination of different techniques can leverage the specific advantages of each method and highlights the effectiveness of the IBSMC for controlling the photovoltaic system.

$$U_{BACKSTEPPING} = 1 - \frac{1}{V_{OUT}}\left(V_{PV} - L\dot{\alpha}_1 - L\left(\frac{\varepsilon_1}{C_{PV}} - K_2\varepsilon_2\right)\right) \quad (26)$$

With

$$\begin{cases} \varepsilon_1 = V_{PV} - V_{REF} \\ \varepsilon_2 = I_L - \alpha_1 \\ \alpha_1 = I_{PV} + C_{PV}(K_1\varepsilon_1 - \dot{V}_{REF}) \end{cases} \quad (27)$$

$$U_{INTEGRAL\ SMC} = 1 - \frac{L}{V_{OUT}}\left(\frac{V_{PV}}{L} - \dot{I}_{PV} + C_{PV}(-K_3\text{sign}(\sigma) + \ddot{V}_{REF} - \lambda\dot{\varepsilon}_1 + K_4\varepsilon_1)\right) \quad (28)$$

With

$$\begin{cases} \varepsilon_1 = V_{PV} - V_{REF} \\ \sigma = \lambda\varepsilon_1 + \dot{\varepsilon}_1 + K_4 \int \varepsilon_1 \\ \dot{\sigma} = \lambda\dot{\varepsilon}_1 + \ddot{\varepsilon}_1 + K_4\varepsilon_1 = -K_3\text{sign}(\sigma) \end{cases} \quad (29)$$

$$U_{BSMC} = 1 - \frac{1}{g_1}\left(-\frac{\varepsilon_1}{C_{PV}} + f_1 - C_{PV}K_1\left(-\frac{s}{C_{PV}} - K_1\varepsilon_1\right) - F\frac{\partial V_{PV}}{\partial t} + g_1(C_1s + C_2\text{Sign}(s))\right) + C_{PV}\frac{\partial^2 V_{REF}}{\partial t^2} \quad (30)$$

$$g_1 = \frac{V_{OUT}}{L}f_1 = \frac{V_{PV}}{L}F = \frac{\partial I_{PV}}{\partial V_{PV}}$$

The simulation of the proposed photovoltaic system was carried out using MATLAB/Simulink. The entire system, including the photovoltaic generator and the DC–DC converter, was fully implemented in this environment, as illustrated in Figure 7. The simulation was performed using the ode45 solver with a discrete

time step of 1×10^{-6} s to ensure high precision of the results. The PV module has the characteristics mentioned above in the modelling section. The energy conversion stage is based on a DC–DC boost converter. The converter parameters are defined as follows: the input capacitor $C_{PV} = 4700$ nF, the inductor $L = 0.35$ mH, the output capacitor $C_{OUT} = 220$ nF, switching frequency $F = 5$ kHz, IGBT, and diode. The structure of the proposed controller, shown in Figure 8, is defined by (24) and (25). The controller parameters were set to $K = 12000$, $K_1 = 700000$, $C_1 = 0.00001$, $C_2 = 2000$, and $C_3 = 50$. These values were obtained through iterative simulation-based tuning to ensure system stability, fast dynamic response, and accurate maximum power point tracking.

Figure 7. PV system model simulation

Figure 8. Proposed controller IBSMC in MATLAB Simulink

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To evaluate the robustness of the proposed control strategy, the photovoltaic system was subjected to variable meteorological conditions, including changes in solar irradiance and temperature, as shown in Figure 9. These variations were as follows: 1000 W/m² and 30 °C from 0 s to 0.9 s; 500 W/m² and 30 °C from 0.9 s to 1.5 s; 500 W/m² and 10 °C from 1.5 s to 1.6 s; 700 W/m² and 10 °C from 1.6 s to 2 s; 700 W/m² and 25 °C from 2 s to 2.2 s; and 950 W/m² and 25 °C from 2.2 s to 3 s. These variations were applied directly to the photovoltaic model during the 3-second simulation.

Figure 10 illustrates the reference voltage V_{REF} generated by the artificial neural network presented above, as well as the voltage of the PV module controlled by the proposed technique, the ANN–IBSMC. The voltage of the PV module using the proposed technique, shown in Figure 10, follows the reference voltage generated by the artificial neural network under different meteorological conditions, with high accuracy, fast convergence, remarkable stability, and strong robustness.

To thoroughly evaluate the performance of the proposed controller, a comparative study of this technique with other techniques proposed in the literature has been explored, such as the hybrid technique ANN-backstepping proposed in [23]–[25], the hybrid technique ANN-ISMC proposed in [26], [27], and finally, the hybrid technique ANN-BSMC proposed in [28]. These four techniques are simulated in MATLAB/Simulink, controlling boost DC-DC converters with the same dimensioning, connected to photovoltaic modules with the same characteristics. The same meteorological conditions from Figure 9 are applied to these four PV systems. The reference voltage generated by the ANN is transmitted to all four control techniques.

Figure 11 illustrates the voltages of the four PV modules and the reference voltage. The proposed method demonstrates excellent accuracy in tracking the reference voltage under different changes in temperature and irradiance. The speed of convergence of the photovoltaic voltage using the proposed method was remarkable during both the rise and fall of the reference voltage. Additionally, the proposed method's stability and robustness are highly satisfactory throughout the simulation period. Figures 12 and 13, respectively, represent the current of the PV module and the error between the PV module voltage and the reference voltage. The convergence speed of the proposed method towards the appropriate current value for the MPP voltage is impressive, and its stability is remarkable. The error epsilon1 of the proposed method quickly converges to zero, practically canceling out, unlike the other techniques, which leave a very small gap between the epsilon1 curve and zero. This gap varies between 0.005 and 0.03, depending on the technique applied to the PV system.

Figure 9. Weather conditions: (a) irradiance and (b) temperature

Figure 10. Photovoltaic voltage

Figure 11. Photovoltaic voltage

Figure 12. Photovoltaic current

Figure 13. Epsilon

Table 1, extracted from Figures 11–13, analytically presents the performance of the voltage and current of the photovoltaic module, as well as the median of the error ε_1 , representing the deviation between the desired and actual voltage of the photovoltaic module, and its accuracy percentage. The voltage of the proposed algorithm is the closest to the reference voltage among all the compared techniques. The IBSMC method achieves the lowest median error of 1.04×10^{-4} , with an accuracy rate of 99.996%, outperforming BSMC (99.976%), ISMC (99.961%), and backstepping (99.901%). Although these percentage differences may seem small, they are significant in photovoltaic systems, where slight voltage deviations can cause considerable power loss. This low error indicates that, for most of the simulation time, the error remains very close to zero, reflecting efficient and stable tracking of the reference voltage. The analysis of the voltage and current ripples presented in the table shows that the IBSMC algorithm provides the lowest voltage and current ripples among all compared methods. For example, the voltage ripple varies between 2.2 mV and 5.9 mV, while the current ripple remains below 1.7 mA, which is significantly lower than in other methods. These low ripples result in a significant reduction of stress on the converter components, particularly on capacitors and inductors, thereby extending their lifespan and improving the overall system reliability. In comparison, the conventional backstepping and integral sliding mode techniques exhibit slightly higher ripples, which could impose additional stress on the converter and affect long-term stability. Thus, the choice of IBSMC not only ensures precise tracking of the maximum power point, achieving 99.996%, but also enhances signal quality and reduces switching stress, which is crucial for applications where durability and energy efficiency of the PV system are priorities. These results highlight the superiority of the IBSMC technique, particularly in terms of the accuracy of tracking the reference value compared to the other techniques considered.

Figure 14 shows the power of the PV module. The proposed method demonstrates a very high convergence speed towards the maximum power point for each variation in meteorological conditions compared to the other simulated techniques. This also results in a very good gain, which is due to the high accuracy in tracking and maintaining the reference voltage. Table 2 presents a comparison of the energy yield and the convergence time of the power for each variation of the meteorological conditions. The data are extracted from Figure 14. The power obtained by the IBSMC strategy exceeds that of the other techniques by a few milliwatts, and its convergence time is significantly faster in all scenarios, outperforming the other methods. This responsiveness demonstrates the controller's ability to efficiently adapt to sudden changes in irradiance and temperature, ensuring high efficiency and optimal extraction of maximum power at all times. The percentage improvements of IBSMC compared to the other methods are calculated based on the average convergence time over the six steps. IBSMC is found to be 8.30% faster than BSMC and 10.31% faster than ISMC on average, while the backstepping method is significantly slower, with a convergence time 61.75% longer than IBSMC. These figures highlight the overall superior dynamic performance of the IBSMC strategy across varying environmental conditions.

Table 1. The performance of the voltage and current of the photovoltaic module

Atmospheric conditions	G (W/m ²) T (°C)	1000	500	500	700	700	950
		30	30	10	10	25	25
V_ref Backstepping	Referentiel Voltage (V)	29.366	29.675	32.495	32.445	30.344	30.13
	V_pv (V)	29.38	29.7	32.525	32.465	30.36	30.14
	Voltage ripple (mV)	17	11	10.4	14	13	16
	I_pv (A)	7.949	3.986	4.018	5.6138	5.585	7.565
	Current ripple (mA)	4.5	1.6	1.5	2	2.2	4
	Error of tracking	$1,562 \cdot 10^{-2}$					
	Accuracy rate (%)	99.901%					
Integral sliding mode controller	V_pv (V)	29.38	29.685	32.504	32.456	30.355	30.145
	Voltage ripple (mV)	4.2	2.5	3.3	3.7	4.4	6.5
	I_pv (A)	7.949	3.9884	4.0186	5.6152	5.5865	7.565
	Current ripple (mA)	1.6	0.4	0.4	0.8	0.8	1.3
	Error of tracking	$1,282 \cdot 10^{-2}$					
	Accuracy rate (%)	99.961%					
	Backstepping sliding mode controller	V_pv (V)	29.375	29.679	32.499	32.452	30.35
Voltage ripple (mV)		5.5	2.5	3	4.2	4.7	6
I_pv (A)		7.9505	3.9892	4.0194	5.616	5.5872	7.566
Current ripple (mA)		1.7	0.4	0.4	0.8	0.9	1.5
Error of tracking		$1,678 \cdot 10^{-3}$					
Accuracy rate (%)		99.976%					
Integral backstepping sliding mode controller		V_pv (V)	29.367	29.676	32.496	32.447	30.345
	Voltage ripple (mV)	4.2	2.2	2.5	4	4	5.5
	I_pv (A)	7.953	3.9897	4.0197	5.617	5.5882	7.568
	Current ripple (mA)	1.7	0.4	0.4	0.8	0.8	1.3
	Error of tracking	$1,04 \cdot 10^{-4}$					
	Accuracy rate (%)	99.996%					

Figure 14. Photovoltaic power

Table 2. Energy yield and the convergence time of the power for each variation of the meteorological conditions

Atmospheric conditions	G (W/m ²)	1000	500	500	700	700	950
	T (°C)	30	30	10	10	25	25
Backstepping	P _{pV} (W)	233.552	118.3955	130.622	182.249	169.574	228.036
	Ripple (mW)	6.6	2.3	2.68	4.65	4.52	10.4
	Tracking time (ms)	20.5	1.6	5	25	5.8	2.4
Integral sliding mode controller	P _{pV} (W)	233.552	118.3975	130.6233	182.2493	169.5745	228.0365
	Ripple (mW)	3.5	1.4	1.57	2.4	2.18	3.7
	Tracking time (ms)	18.5	0.4	3.6	0.7	1.6	0.9
Backstepping sliding mode controller	P _{pV} (W)	233.553	118.3985	130.6235	182.2497	169.575	228.0375
	Ripple (mW)	3.2	1.38	1.35	2.2	2.2	3.9
	Tracking time (ms)	18.5	0.4	3.6	0.6	1.4	0.8
Integral backstepping sliding mode controller	P _{pV} (W)	233.554	118.3988	130.6236	182.2505	169.5755	228.039
	Ripple (mW)	3.2	1.38	1.35	2.3	2.2	3.8
	Tracking time (ms)	18	0.35	3.4	0.3	0.6	0.4

To analyze the sensitivity and robustness of this controller, three sets of simulations were conducted: to study the impact of slight changes in controller parameters, the presence of input disturbances, and the gradual degradation of components. Figure 15 shows the PV voltage and power under $\pm 5\%$ variation of the controller parameters. The voltage takes about 2 ms longer to reach the reference value when the parameters are decreased by 5%, while an increase of 5% causes an overshoot of 30 mV. The PV power also exhibits slightly increased ripples. Figure 16 illustrates the PV voltage and power in the presence of input disturbances, corresponding to inaccuracies in the voltage and current sensors. Disturbances of 1% to 5% cause a deviation of 250 mV for 1% disturbances and up to 400 mV with unwanted ripples for 5% disturbances during rapid changes in weather conditions. This variation affects the generated power by 0.076% for 1% disturbances and 0.13% for 5% disturbances. Figure 17 presents the PV voltage and power under 5% and 10% degradation of the converter components. The voltage convergence speed slightly increases, but abrupt changes in weather conditions lead to parasitic ripples of 80 mV for 5% degradation and 240 mV for 10%. The power exhibits slightly larger ripples. These three sets of simulations demonstrate that the proposed controller and the overall system are robust. The system remains stable under $\pm 5\%$ variations of the controller parameters and can tolerate input disturbances or sensor inaccuracies up to 1%. Moreover, the overall performance is only slightly affected by the degradation of the converter components.

The proposed hybrid control structure, combining integral backstepping and SMC, has been designed to ensure real-time implementation while maintaining high robustness against uncertainties and external disturbances. The performed sensitivity and robustness analysis confirms the system's stability and reliability under various conditions, directly supporting the feasibility of practical implementation on a hardware platform. The tuning of the control parameters does not require significant effort, as the gains are derived from explicit analytical relations. Moreover, the control law relies on simple arithmetic operations such as multiplications, additions, and integrations, minimizing the computational load. At a switching frequency of 5 kHz, the total computation time per control period is estimated between 50 and 70 μ s, including signal

acquisition, control law computation, and PWM signal update. This duration remains well below the sampling period (200 μ s), ensuring reliable real-time execution on modern microcontrollers. The integration of the ANN, consisting of a single hidden layer with 50 neurons, does not significantly increase the computational burden thanks to the optimized number of operations. Evaluating the network per control period requires less than 20 μ s additional time, which remains compatible with a 5 kHz sampling frequency. An efficient implementation can therefore be achieved on a DSP or a modern microcontroller, providing the required computing power and precision for real-time processing.

Figure 15. Sensitivity analysis of the proposed controller with $\pm 5\%$ variation of the controller nominal values: (a) PV module voltage and (b) PV module power

Figure 16. Robustness analysis of the proposed controller under input disturbances with 1% and 5% noise: (a) PV module voltage and (b) PV module power

Figure 17. Robustness analysis of the proposed controller under converter component degradation with 5% and 10% reductions of the nominal component values: (a) PV module voltage and (b) PV module power

Finally, the proposed structure offers promising potential for implementation on real hardware and deployment on an experimental bench or in field conditions, paving the way for future experimental validation. The combination of hybrid control and the ANN, along with the controller's manageable computational load, makes this approach particularly suitable for embedded photovoltaic systems requiring speed, stability, and adaptability.

5. CONCLUSION

This paper has presented a hybrid MPPT technique called ANN-IBSMC. This approach combines artificial neural networks with a novel controller that integrates the backstepping technique, its integral component, and SMC. The synergy of these control methods enables near-perfect accuracy (99.996%) by effectively eliminating the error between the actual PV module voltage and the reference voltage provided by the neural network. The strategy also achieves a very fast convergence time, surpassing, on average, ANN-BSMC by 8.3%, ANN-ISMC by 10.32%, and ANN-backstepping by 61.75%. It exhibits a sensitivity margin tolerating $\pm 5\%$ variations in controller parameters, $\pm 1\%$ input disturbances or sensor inaccuracies, as well as a $\pm 5\%$ to $\pm 10\%$ degradation of the converter component values. Furthermore, its computational load remains acceptable, allowing implementation on moderately capable microprocessors. This level of performance ensures highly accurate and rapid tracking of the maximum power point, even under varying weather conditions, thereby enabling a significant increase in electrical energy production, equivalent to several tens of kilowatt-hours for large-scale photovoltaic systems.

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C : Conceptualization

M : Methodology

So : Software

Va : Validation

Fo : Formal analysis

I : Investigation

R : Resources

D : Data Curation

O : Writing - Original Draft

E : Writing - Review & Editing

Vi : Visualization

Su : Supervision

P : Project administration

Fu : Funding acquisition

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

Authors state no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author, [NZ], upon reasonable request.

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